

Optical Computing for Artificial Neural Network Implementations

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Abstract—Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have recently gained recognition as a valuable tool to aid in the solution of difficult computing problems. Despite an abundance of work in the application and mathematical foundations of ANNs there currently exists no consensus on how to implement ANNs in hardware. The goal of this paper is to motivate the use of optical computing technologies to meet the huge computational burden presented by ANNs and to provide an analytical perspective on ANN implementation by addressing issues and design tradeoffs.

INTRODUCTION

Although computers have increased performance by an order of magnitude every five to ten years since their inception many obstacles remain in applying them to real-world situations. Conventional computers must be programmed (an expensive proposition) and cannot deal well with new, unforeseen inputs. Further, these devices cannot easily recognize patterns (such as speech or handwriting) causing them to interface with humans in an unnatural manner. These inadequacies, together with our inability to sustain the rapid growth in performance of conventional computer hardware has motivated the study of alternative methods.

Artificial Neural Networks represent an unusual, biologically-inspired strategy to do computing. Although ANNs are not a new development, born in the work of McCulloch and Pitts in the 1940s and 1950s, only recently (1980s) have important breakthroughs been made to allow them to become an effective computational paradigm. These systems work well in many areas where traditional computers fail: ANNs are particularly promising in *artificial perception* tasks such as speech recognition and machine vision. They have found increased use in adaptive signal processing and adaptive control theory as well.

The response and characteristics of present models of artificial neural networks are primarily investigated by simulation on conventional computers or parallel processing machines. Figure 1 shows the performance obtainable with commercially available simulators in terms of interconnections (storage) and interconnections per second (speed). This should be compared with current and future

Figure 1 - ANN Implementation Requirements

application requirements. It becomes obvious that today's hardware capabilities are limiting the development of neural network research. The fundamental drawback of the simulators is that much of the spatial and temporal parallelism, inherent to ANNs, is lost and that the computing time of the simulated net, especially for large associations of neurons, grows to such orders of magnitude that a timely response may not be achievable. While current research requirements necessarily conform to electronic implementations (semiconductor) it is apparent that optical technology can open the doors for new research. As application requirements begin to outpace the capabilities of software simulation and electronic realizations, it makes sense to think about designing specialized optical hardware.

There currently exists no consensus on how to implement ANNs into hardware. Although optical technologies hold the most promise in the long term, electronics are currently favorable because of the maturity of the technology and the level of integration. However there remain many largely unaddressed questions with regard to electronic ANN implementation: How do we deal with the massive number of interconnections required (the *connectivity problem*)? Can we supply the large amount of storage required? Can we provide flexibility for learning and adaptation without sacrificing performance? What are the advantages and disadvantages of continuous vs. discrete time, analog vs. digital valued, and literal vs. virtual implementations?

One goal of this paper is to provide some perspective on the implementation of ANNs. This will be done by discussing issues and examples. Although it is assumed that the reader is familiar with the pertinent aspects of ANNs, they will be briefly reviewed in the next section.

NEURAL NETWORK FUNDAMENTALS

Neural Networks primarily operate in two modes; *learning* mode and *recall* or *relaxed* mode. These may both be running concurrently. *Learning* involves the update of weights to strengthen or weaken network connections while *recall* involves processing inputs to produce outputs. As we propagate signals through the network we require two basic operations: *processing* and *communication*. We shall see that these may be mathematically represented as a matrix-vector multiplication.

The basic component of a neural network is the neuron model. A number of models have been constructed to describe the behavior of neurons in biological nervous systems. These have been inspired by different goals. Some describe the operation of neurons in great mathematical detail, usually to study them from a neuropsychology standpoint. Others assume some simplifications for ease of implementation, making them more amenable to performing computations. Since we are interested in performing computations, we will discuss the latter type of model.

Figure 2 shows the general structure of most simplified neuron models. The neuron receives a set of input signals, x_i , which are multiplied by a corresponding set of weighting factors, w_i . All of the weighted input signals are added up to produce n , the complete input to the neuron. An *activation function*, F , operates on the sum of the weighted neuron inputs ($\sum_i w_i x_i$), transforming it into an output signal which can be transmitted to other neurons. The activation function is usually some type of nonlinearity such as a sigmoid ($\{1 + e^{-in}\}^{-1}$), hyperbolic tangent or signum function. The weight w_0 is the threshold value Θ which biases the firing of the neuron. By convention the input x_0 is set to unity. The weighting factors play an important role in the neuron model. A larger weighting factor will serve to increase the sensitivity of the neuron to a particular input.

Figure 2 - Neuron Model.

The real power of a Neural Network emanates in from it's connections and it's consequent ability to form associations. The vast majority of network models are variations on two principal topologies; *feedback (recursive)* and *feedforward* networks. The latter is shown in figure 3. This network has an input layer, two hidden layers, and an output layer. The number of neurons in each layer and the number of hidden layers is an architectural decision that is often application dependent. The feedforward network structure produces a nonlinear mapping between the input vector, $\underline{\mu}$, and the

output vector, \underline{X} as described in figure 3 (F is a nonlinear activation function). In the *recursive* network shown in

Figure 3. Feedforward Network Topology

figure 4, each neuron receives a weighted output from all the neurons in the single-layer net. This system receives and input vector of u_i s and iterates according to the equation $x_i = F(\sum w_j x_j + u_i)$. This operation is used to implement an associative memory; the network is supplied with a partial input pattern and after iterating it converges to the complete and closest pattern. The output of a recursive ANN is described by a trajectory of vectors over time rather than a single vector as in the feedforward case.

Regardless of the network topology, all neural networks are fundamentally vector mappers, input vectors are mapped to some output vector through some sequence of nonlinear transformations. The weights of a network define the nonlinear mappings or associations to be implemented. These weights are adjusted when the network is in a *training mode* by some *learning laws*. There are a great many learning laws and much attention is focused on this area. Two general classes of learning procedures exist. In *unsupervised learning*, network models are first presented with an input vector from the set of possible network inputs.

Figure 4 - Recursive Network Topology

The network rule adjusts the weights so that input examples are grouped into classes based upon their statistical properties. In *supervised learning* the network is presented with a set of training examples (inputs and desired outputs). The output error is then minimized by modifying the weights. In general this is a long, arduous process. This has caused much of the skepticism among ANN critics. Efficient learning is one of the primary focuses of ANN research. As discussed below the network propagation time has a direct effect on training.

DESIGN ISSUES

Literal vs. Virtual Implementation and The Connectivity Problem

One fundamental question in electronic ANN hardware design is whether to implement the network literally or not. In other words, how many virtual neurons should be hosted on each physical processor? The extreme cases are the serial implementation of an ANN algorithm on a general-purpose uniprocessor (full virtualization), and the fully parallel implementation of one processing element per algorithmic neuron (no virtualization).

The feasibility of literal implementation depends partially upon the size of the network. To realize a fully connected recursive network (see figure 4) of n nodes requires n^2 connections. While the realization of a multi-layer feedforward network (see figure 3) containing ℓ layers with N_i nodes in each layer requires $\sum_{i=2}^{\ell} N_i N_{i-1}$ connections. Literal realizations of larger networks may not be plausible because of the overwhelming number of connections and the amount physical space they would require. The size of the network and the ability of the technology to accommodate this massive communication burden are key to the decision on literality.

The *speed* of a network is always an important consideration. It affects the propagation time (time to pass signals through the network) in both the learning and relaxed modes. We compare the forward (relaxed mode) propagation time of a literal implementation, t_{lit} , with that of a virtual implementation, t_{vir} , for the multi-layer feedforward network of figure 3. We assume that the network has N neurons in ℓ layers, and C connections. The virtual realization of this network contains P physical processors (analog or digital) connected by B hardware buses. We see that for the literal case

$$t_{lit} = \ell t_{proc} + (\ell-1)t_{com}$$

where t_{proc} is the neuron's processing time and t_{com} is the communication time representing the latency time of connections between layers. The virtual net requires a forward propagation time given by

$$t_{vir} = \frac{N}{\mu P} \hat{t}_{proc} + C(\hat{t}_{bus} + \lambda_B) \rho[P_{send} \neq P_{recv}] + C \hat{t}_{local} \rho[P_{send} = P_{recv}]$$

where \hat{t}_{proc} , \hat{t}_{bus} , and \hat{t}_{local} represent the neuron processing time, the transmission delay of the bus, and the transmission delay to send a signal over a local bus internal to a processor (this may be a memory access). We include μ as a processor utilization factor. The term λ_B symbolizes the overhead in communication from bus request collisions (usually $\lambda_B \gg \hat{t}_{bus}$). λ_B can be expressed as

$$\lambda_B = \frac{C}{\alpha B} t_{bus}$$

where α represents bus utilization. We note that the

overhead factors, μ and α , are monotonically increasing functions of P and C - for simplification we shall assume both to be unity (best case for literal implementation). A virtual neuron may signal another neuron in either the same or a different host processor, denoted as $P_{send} = P_{recv}$ and $P_{send} \neq P_{recv}$ respectively. Assuming that virtual neurons are uniformly distributed across all the processors the probabilities for these two cases is given by

$$\rho[P_{send} = P_{recv}] = \frac{1}{P} \quad \text{and}$$

$$\rho[P_{send} \neq P_{recv}] = \frac{P-1}{P}$$

We will assume the virtual implementation incurs no penalty in processing or communication times, that is $t_{proc} = \hat{t}_{proc}$ and $t_{com} = \hat{t}_{bus} = \hat{t}_{local}$. With these simplifications we may express the forward propagation time as

$$t_{vir} = \frac{N}{P} t_{proc} + \left[\frac{C^2(P-1) + CBP}{BP} \right] t_{com}$$

It becomes obvious what we loose in virtualization when we compare t_{lit} and t_{vir} : The propagation time of the ideal, literal implementation does not increase with network size (N or C); ℓ (usually between 2 and 4, [3]) is an architectural decision, independent of N and C . The virtual implementation's communication time increases quadratically with C or roughly as a function of N^2 since $C = \sum_{i=2}^{\ell} N_i N_{i-1} \approx O(N^2)$ and the processing time increases linearly with N . For large networks t_{vir} becomes excessive, particularly if P and B are small.

Of course there are practical considerations. How many processors or busses should we use? This often becomes a question of *efficiency and cost*. Suppose we have N virtual nodes with C connections out of each of them (now $C = N_{i+1}$, the number of nodes in the next layer). If there are P physical processors, then the probability that a particular connection will not be directed to any one processor (causing it to go idle) is

$$\rho(\text{miss/conn}) = \frac{P-1}{P}$$

and the probability that none of the C connections made in a single broadcast step are implemented on this processor is

$$\rho(\text{miss}) = \left[\frac{P-1}{P} \right]^C$$

This probability is essentially an inefficiency factor. For $P = C$ this is approximately equal to $1/e$, since

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{x}{x-1} \right]^x \approx \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{x+1}{x} \right]^x = e$$

Thus, asymptotic performance (total useful computation within 37% of the maximum achievable by an infinite number of processors) is reached for a number of processors comparable to the number of connections out of each unit.

Much fewer than C processors, however, would imply significantly reduced computational throughput.

For electronic implementation processors are relatively expensive - for large networks it is usually not practical to have a literal realization nor to even have C processors. This causes reduced performance by degrading forward propagation time and efficiency as shown above.

Digital vs. Analog Implementation

Historically, ANN simulation has favored digital devices while dedicated ANN implementations have used primarily analog devices. The motivation for these areas is slightly different. Simulation investigates ANN properties and must be done on a general-purpose *digital* computer. Dedicated ANNs, which work in one application area, have followed the most successful model known, the biological (*analog*) model. Both of these paradigms have particular advantages and as a result, somewhat of a controversy has developed. Analog supporters point to the fact that analog devices can process more than one bit (of accuracy) per transistor leading to greater levels of integration which is key to the ability to support literal implementations. Analog devices perform the pervasive multiply-accumulate operations in parallel as a result of physics, making them potentially quicker. Those that advocate digital devices have pointed to the superior noise immunity, more sophisticated time multiplexing techniques (which better support virtualization), and better fabrication processes associated with digital VLSI. Further, digital devices are more easily programmed and more capable of supporting the large dynamic range that network weights require to implement gradient learning algorithms.

We may observe the slower execution times for digital networks by re-examining the forward propagation time discussed above. In particular we investigate the processing time, t_{proc} . For a single neuron with n inputs, as shown in figure 2, the computations required include n multiplications, $(n-1)$ additions, and a nonlinear activation function approximation. We write the execution time for a single neuron as

$$t_{proc}(neuron) = n t_{mult} + (n-1) t_{add} + t_{act}$$

Realizing that a fully connected feedforward network provides each neuron of layer i with $n_{i-1} + 1$ input connections (we account for the threshold weight) we can easily derive an expression for the processing time:

$$t_{proc}(network) = \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} [(n_{i-1} + 1) n_i (t_{mult} + t_{add}) + t_{act}]$$

where ℓ is the number of layers and n_i denotes the number of nodes in layer i . It is clear that the processing time for the digital case increases quadratically ($O(n^2)$) with network size. Analog implementations do not generally suffer from this problem because additions, multiplications, and even the activation function may result directly from the device and circuit characteristics.

Another consideration is cost. To investigate this we first reflect upon ANN structure; there are two basic operations, computation and communication. These can be dissected into three fundamental architectural tenets; processing, memory, and communication. One approach to a cost analysis would compare the price of performing these three functions in the analog and the digital case. We follow that approach.

The cost of interconnecting points in analog and digital technology is essentially the same assuming the "wiring" process and material to be identical for both cases. It becomes a question of the amount of interconnection required and the space it consumes. We will assume that after taking noise margins into account a particular analog device provides us with β bits of accuracy which, for analog implementations, is propagated over a single interconnect. For equivalent accuracy we will then require β digital interconnects for each analog interconnect. We can establish a simple relationship between the relative costs as

$$C_{interconnect}(digital) = \beta \cdot C_{interconnect}(analog)$$

where $\beta = \text{Int}(3.2d + 1)$ and d is the number of decimal digits required ($\beta \geq 1$ and β is assumed to be independent of network size). Following the same argument for the processing costs (two cases differ in quantity of processing devices required for equivalent accuracies) we can assert a linear relationship there as well:

$$C_{processing}(digital) = \beta' \cdot C_{processing}(analog)$$

Where β' is proportional to β ; we shall assume $\beta' = \beta$.

We now compare the relative costs to store the weights in memory. Fortunately, an applicable analysis exists in Wiener [9] which we shall site.

Normally we would expect a more accurate device to cost more than a less accurate one and we assume, for the purposes of this argument that the cost, C_{memory} , is proportional to accuracy. In fact, if one thinks of the device as a meter with a pointer that must finish in one of n well defined regions, it is clear that having just one region would not convey any information and should not contribute to the cost. Therefore the cost of the device should be counted only for regions in excess of 1 and may be written as $C_{memory} = (n - 1)A$, where A is some arbitrary constant which depends upon the method of manufacture. The amount of information, β , contained in n messages is $\beta = \log_2 n$ bits hence the cost equation may be written as $C_{memory} = (2^\beta - 1)A$. The key question here is: 'Is it better to distribute the information over several less accurate (digital) devices or keep it all in one highly accurate (analog) device?'. If we were to divide the information β over two devices the total cost will be $C_{memory} = 2(2^{\beta/2} - 1)A$. Similarly by dividing β over N devices the cost becomes $C_{memory} = N(2^{\beta/N} - 1)A$. It may be shown that this function decreases as N increases. For example, with $A = 1$ and $\beta = 16$, we have:

N	C_{memory}
1	65,535
2	510
4	30
8	24
16	16

We observe that the cost function is minimized when each memory device has only two states (when $N = \beta$). This implies that if information is to be stored at all, it can be done most cheaply in binary code with digital devices. We have

$$C_{memory}(analog) = \frac{2^\beta - 1}{\beta} C_{memory}(digital)$$

using $N = 1$ for the analog case and $N = \beta$ for the digital case. The total cost can now be found by summing the component costs;

$$\begin{aligned} C_{total}(analog) &= \sum_{i=proc,intercon,mem} C_i(analog) \\ &= \frac{1}{\beta} [C_{processing}(digital) + C_{interconnect}(digital)] \\ &\quad + \frac{2^\beta - 1}{\beta} C_{memory}(digital) . \end{aligned}$$

We may assume that $C_{processing}(digital)$, $C_{interconnect}(digital)$ and $C_{memory}(digital)$ are all linearly related (differing only by a constant factor) and they are independent of the signal accuracy β . We can say that

$$C_{processing}(digital) = \alpha \cdot C_{interconnection}(digital) = \sigma \cdot C_{memory}(digital) \quad (\alpha, \sigma \geq 0)$$

For simplicity we shall assume $\alpha, \sigma = 1$. It then becomes clear that as our precision requirements increase the cost ratio of analog memory over digital memory increases exponentially:

$$C_{total}(analog) = \frac{2^\beta + 1}{3\beta} C_{total}(digital)$$

where β represents network accuracy requirements (as well as the number of bits for the digital case). We may also observe that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\text{cost of analog}}{\text{cost of digital}} &= \frac{2^\beta + 1}{3\beta} \quad \text{and} \\ \lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\text{cost of analog}}{\text{cost of digital}} &= \infty \end{aligned}$$

We conclude that electronic digital implementations are generally more cost-efficient for any given precision.

Continuous vs. Discrete Implementation

Literality and the number of quantization levels (as discussed above) are *spatial* decisions for ANN implementors. We have not yet considered the *temporal*

aspect. The issue of whether to use asynchronous, continuous time devices or synchronous, discrete implementation involves efficiency and optimization in time. Although the question is often entangled with the issues discussed above, it need not be. It is true that analog implementations tend to operate in continuous time and digital devices are usually discrete but hybrids abound. Asynchronous-digital ANNs (see [7]) and synchronous-analog realizations do exist.

Continuous operation is more biologically accurate and almost essential in many of the recursive networks often used as associative memories [3]. But discrete implementations may simulate continuous time by stochastically firing the neurons [12]. Discrete implementations tend to have larger network delay time due to the overhead in synchronization mechanisms (these mechanisms carry a penalty in terms of chip area). The tradeoff made here is between smaller, faster, more biologically accurate implementation and slower, more flexible, operation.

THE ROLE OF OPTICS

We have seen that we are presented with somewhat of a dilemma when we attempt to implement ANNs electronically. While digital implementation may be more flexible and perhaps more cost-efficient, it lacks the speed and simplicity of its analog counterpart. Further, we are pushed towards virtual realizations because of the *connectivity* problem and the ubiquitous multiply-accumulate operations. Optical computing technology, though in its infancy, clearly has the potential to alleviate some of these problems by providing much denser interconnection, quicker propagation, and a natural parallelism which may be tailored to ANN designs.

As mentioned above, the neural network paradigm involves two fundamental activities: **processing** and **communication**. Optics has a very natural and evident advantage in the area of communication due to the *non-interfering property* of light. Many photonic signals may be transmitted through each other and in the same space with no information lost upon signal recovery. In electronics, capacitance and electromagnetic interference limit the speed and degree of miniaturization attainable.

In order to perform the processing activity optical signals must be able to carry information. In electronics we encode information as voltages, currents, or phase and frequency data. Similarly in optics we may encode information as amplitudes, intensities, polarization, phase or frequency. But some of these encoding schemes may require more expensive, coherent (single frequency) light sources such as lasers. One of the simplest ways to encode information is to use transmittance (intensity). This allows one to use incoherent light sources.

Upon encoding the information we next must perform weighting and thresholding operations on signals. The

weighting operation is usually a multiplication (although other operations may be used - an XOR is used in a design example below). Figure 5 below shows the design of a simple analog optical multiplier. The information on plate 1, $f_1(x,y)$, is fourier transformed by the lens L_2 and then inverse fourier transformed by L_3 so that the reverse image, $f_1(-x,-y)$, is projected upon the second plate containing $f_2(x,y)$. The transmittance of the combination at any arbitrary point is the transmittance of the product of the individual images at that point: $f_3(x,y) = f_1(-x,-y) \cdot f_2(x,y)$.

Figure 5 - An optical multiplier [8].

We have already seen that the weighting and multiply-accumulate operations may be performed as a vector-matrix multiplication. We may extend the idea of figure 5 to produce a parallel optical matrix-vector multiplier as shown in figure 6. The pixels along the vertical columns of the

Figure 6 - A parallel matrix-vector multiplier [8].

image introduced at P_1 have identical transmittance values. The information of plane P_1 thus corresponds to that of a vector, say \mathbf{b} of n elements. These columns of light can be superimposed on a matrix mask located at P_3 . The information of the matrix mask corresponds to that of a matrix, \mathbf{A} , of dimensions $n \times n$. The product, \mathbf{C} ($\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{A}$), of the stored matrix and the input vector is then fourier transformed along only the horizontal direction by the cylindrical lens, L_3 , which is then inverse fourier transformed by the biconvex lens, L_4 . Consequently at the output plane P_5 we obtain the column vector of the product \mathbf{C} such that it's m th row consists of the sum of products $\sum a_{mj} b_j$. Figure 7 shows a three-dimensional view of optical matrix-vector multiplication. A *spatial light modulator* (SLM) may be used to form a weight mask. The SLM may be thought of as a controllable transparency which can adjust the transmittance of each of its pixels. With proper focusing optics (cylindrical lenses, not shown) the input beams' transmittance is weighted by a particular row of the weight mask SLM to

produce an output transmittance. We may note that this scheme performs all the $O(n^2)$ multiply-accumulate operations in parallel. The capacity is limited only by the level of miniaturization which can be achieved.

Figure 7 - Matrix-Vector Multiplier using SLM [8]

Upon completion of the weighting operation thresholding must be accomplished. Thresholding involves the application of some nonlinear activation function. This can be divided into two broad categories; *external thresholding*, and *internal thresholding* [13]. External thresholding is distinguished by using electronics to apply the nonlinearity. In internal thresholding nonlinear optical devices must be used. Although electronic devices are clearly more adept at performing nonlinear transformations, their use requires a conversion process (optic to/from electronic). This is generally costly in terms of speed, power consumption and device size. In practice, external thresholding is more popular since nonlinear optical devices are relatively immature.

Design Example

Content-Addressable Network

The Content-Addressable Network (CAN) is an electro-optic implementation of a pattern-classifying neural network proposed by Brodsky, Mardsen, and Guest [6]. CAN represents a simple, efficient hybrid system which exploits the particular strengths of optics and electronics, using each technology to do what it does cheaply and well.

Binary classification would be expensive using a conventional continuous-valued network model on a digital machine. The backpropagation learning algorithm has been observed to require 8 or more bits at each interconnection. Without this level of precision the network may not converge to a learned solution. CAN avoids this issue by using binary values for each connection weight and node output. This reduction in accuracy requirements allows for the utilization of digital memories which, as argued earlier, are expected to be cheaper than analog memories. The activation function is also binary rather than a sigmoid or tanh function.

Figure 8 shows a single layer of the CAN network. Each horizontal row of the weight matrix represent a node whose weights, m_{ij} , are exclusive-ORed with the elements of the input vector, \mathbf{V} . We should recall that the exclusive-OR operation will produce a 1 (high or true) output only if these

two values are different. We shall abbreviate the exclusive-OR operation as "XOR" and denote it as " \oplus ". The result of each node's XOR operations are summed to form the

Figure 8 - Single CAN Layer [6]

summation vector, D . This sum is also called the *Hamming distance* and is a measure of how different the node's weight and input vectors are. We should note that the standard weighting by multiplication has been replaced by the exclusive-OR operation. This is similar to the concept of *associative memory* (mentioned with figure 4) which uses the Hamming distance to associate similar strings. A candidate input string is used to interrogate a memory in parallel. Figure 9 shows the structure of one such memory.

Figure 9 - Associative Memory [6]

A Hamming distance is computed between part of each memory word and the interrogator string. The memory with the smallest Hamming distance produces the output. The last (uninterrogated) portion of the memory cell is displayed. In this way an input string is *associated* with a particular output.

The summation vector, D , is computed optically using a technique similar to the matrix-vector multiplication mentioned above. We may express this as

$$m_{j,i} \oplus v_i = m_{j,i} \bar{v}_i + \bar{m}_{j,i} v_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } m_{j,i} \neq v_i \\ 0 & \text{for } m_{j,i} = v_i \end{cases}$$

$$d_j = \sum_i m_{j,i} \oplus v_i \rightarrow D = M \oplus V$$

We then apply a threshold to the summation values to obtain an output.

$$O_j = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } d_j > \theta_j \\ 0 & \text{for } d_j < \theta_j \end{cases}$$

Figure 10 shows the overall CAN implementation. Note the efficiency of the system, requiring only two spatial light modulators (SLMs) to convert electronic signals into optical ones, a polarized beam splitter (PBS) to direct the light, a cylindrical lens to focus the light causing row elements to overlap, and a charge-coupled device (CCD) detector which producing electronic signals proportional to the light intensity. Two PCs are used for the electronic-thresholding

Figure 10 - CAN Implementation [6]

portion, although special purpose hardware could also be designed if performance became a problem. A plane wave is transmitted into the PBS and reflected onto the vector SLM plane. The vector information is then reflected back through the PBS onto the matrix SLM plane. The overlap of the vector and matrix information at the PBS performs a logical AND operation. This comes about because of the special encoding employed for the vector and weight information. This is shown in figure 11(a). Two pieces of information being reflected onto each other would normally be an OR operation but because of the encoding scheme shown in figure 11(a) an AND operation results - full transmittance is called a logical zero, no transmittance is called a logical one. When the light source is reflected upon a logical one datum it's polarization is rotated 90° causing it not to pass through the PBS nor contribute to the summation vector, D . This then produces an area of no transmittance wherever there is a logical one. Opposite dual-rail encodings are applied as shown in figure 11(b). This opposite encoding allows one to generate an exclusive-OR function (see figure 11(c)). The output is formed when the cylindrical lens focuses the light onto the CCD. The overlap of two digital patterns encoded as transmittance values results in an OR operation. The cylindrical lens then focuses the light essentially adding all the transmittance values and forming a single column of dual-rails on the front face of the CCD. The CCD produces electronic signals proportional to

Figure 11 - CAN Encoding Scheme [6]

the intensity detected at each bit position in the CCD array. This is then thresholded by the network PC to calculate the output vector, \mathbf{O} . If we are in recall mode and this is the hidden representation, the result is passed to the application PC so that it may be stored into the vector SLM. The network PC must concurrently update the weight matrix. If we are in learning mode we want to use this output and stored information about the desired output (target) to form an error which will be used to update the threshold and weight matrix. The learning algorithm calculations take place in the network PC.

We may compare the forward propagation time for the CAN with that derived previously for a virtual network. Here the forward propagation time is given as

$$t_{prop} = n \cdot t_{layer} = n \cdot [t_{opt} + t_{thr} + t_{SLM}]$$

where n represents the number of layers, t_{layer} is the propagation time through a single layer, t_{opt} is the optical propagation time through the optical portion, t_{thr} is the time to perform the thresholding function electronically, and t_{SLM} is the time to address the SLMs. CAN's performance is considerably better than that for electronic digital or virtual implementations discussed above. In practice the propagation time is limited by the electronics and SLM access/latency time, t_{thr} and t_{SLM} . The potential for fully literal implementations is evident if we can achieve the required miniaturization of the SLM pixels. Dimensions of 256x256 pixels are available in SLMs today. This equates to 65,536 interconnections from a single weight mask. The electronic portion could be implemented so that all of the thresholds were applied in parallel as they are presented from the CCD. Currently it is the optical devices that limit the performance obtainable.

CONCLUSION

Several of the principal issues, challenges, and tradeoffs for the implementation of neural networks have been discussed. These include the question of analog vs. digital implementation, virtual vs. literal realizations, as well as speed and cost considerations in implementing a network. We have seen that there is a large range of possible implementation strategies, from simulation to literal physical imitation, each with its own strength and weaknesses. Optical technologies have the potential to satisfy the considerable computational burden presented by these

networks. Ultimately, design tradeoffs will be made for the problem at hand. Several generalizations have been made which will hopefully help to filter the 'clutter' in the field. Hopefully the scientific community will continue to search for efficient neural network implementations: The potential rewards are very great.

REFERENCES

- [1] R.P. Lippman, "An Introduction to Computing with Neural Nets", *IEEE ASSP Magazine*, April 1987, pp. 4-22
- [2] Don R. Rush, "Progress in Supervised Neural Networks: What's New Since Lippman?", *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, January 1993, pp. 8-39
- [3] Philip D. Wasserman, *Neural Computing, Theory and Practice*, 1989, Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York.
- [4] Carver A. Mead, *Analog VLSI and Neural Systems*, 1989, Addison-Wesley, Massachusetts.
- [5] *Silicon Architectures for Neural Nets*, Ed. by M. Sami and J. Calzadilla-Daguerra, 1991, North-Holland, New York.
- [6] Stephen A. Brodsky, Gary C Mardsen, and Clark C Guest, "Optical Matrix-Vector Implementation of the Content-Addressable Network", *Applied Optics*, March 1993, pp. 1338-1345
- [7] A.F. Murray, "Asynchronous VLSI Neural Networks Using Pulse-Stream Arithmetic", *Journal of Solid State Circuits*, June 1988, pp. 688-697
- [8] Mohammad A. Karim and Abdul A.S. Awwal, *Optical Computing*, 1992, John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- [9] Norbert Wiener, *Cybernetics*, 1986, MIT Press, Massachusetts.
- [10] *Darpa Neural Network Study*, November 1988, AFCEA International Press
- [11] Alastair D. McAuley, *Optical Computing Architectures*, 1991, John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- [12] Mathew S. Melton, "The ThMANN VLSI Chip", *IEEE Trans on Neural Networks*, May 1992, pp. 375-383
- [13] Steven C. Gustafson, "Thresholding and Weighting in Optical Computing", *Optical Computing*, Ed. by Raymond Arrathoon, 1989, Marcel Dekker Inc., New York.